

Open Science NL community engagement strategy

Authors: Team Open Science NL
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Summary and introduction

Two of the key tasks of Open Science NL are¹:

- to “identify, prioritise and fund temporary initiatives and projects aimed at sustainably anchoring Open Science in the Netherlands”;
- to “provide a forum for knowledge sharing and stimulate exchange through communities of practice”.

These tasks are interrelated. Effectively addressing the first task requires engaging with the relevant communities of practice to identify key challenges and potential solutions to those challenges. Funding instruments developed under the first task will, in turn, help address the second task by strengthening existing and upcoming communities.

This document outlines Open Science NL’s strategy for community engagement along two complementary lines of action:

- through broad community consultation;
- through expert advisory panels.

Broad community consultation is essential to ensure that the various stakeholder groups and their voices are heard and included. Advisory panels, smaller groups of independent experts, advise the Open Science NL programme leaders on developing effective work programmes and funding instruments that take into account community needs and advance the transition to open science. This two-fold approach will allow Open Science NL to deliver on its tasks in an inclusive and transparent manner and will help facilitate the cultural change that is needed to foster the adoption of open science practices in the Netherlands.

¹ [Convenant regieorgaan Open Science](#), article 2, page 3.

The Open Science NL approach to community engagement

To effectively address its key tasks, Open Science NL proposes to actively engage with the community along two complementary lines of action: through broad, open community consultation and through the establishment of independent advisory panels. The goal is to ensure that Open Science NL receives broad, diverse and inclusive input directly from the community at various stages in the process of developing and carrying out its work programme. It is also imperative that the processes by which Open Science NL engages with the community are maximally open, transparent and inclusive.

Building on the National Open Science Programme

Open Science NL envisions to build on the strengths of the approach taken by the National Programme Open Science (NPOS), the predecessor of Open Science NL. The NPOS Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda includes contributions from a large fraction of the community (see: [Report on the Open Consultation of the NPOS2030 Ambition Document](#)). Through an open consultation, 78 institutions, networks, communities and individuals contributed to the Ambition Document. The Rolling Agenda was written by several writing teams, and had the support of partners involved in the NPOS Steering Committee, the Advisory Board and the Rolling Agenda editorial board. Three 'tafels' (tables), each associated with one of the three NPOS thematic programme lines (FAIR data, open access and citizen science), contributed to the process of developing both the Ambition Document and the Rolling Agenda. Each table consisted of 10-15 members, who represented various Dutch organisations and held an interest in the corresponding theme.

Overall, the NPOS community engagement strategy led to the development of a comprehensive Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda, supported by the community. As a result, the Rolling Agenda serves as an important starting point for the Open Science NL work programme. However, in the NPOS process, the wider community did not have a direct way to contribute to all the thematic programme lines, as this was a task designated to the table and writing and editorial teams. Furthermore, the tables did not have terms of reference, which made their scope and composition undefined.

Open Science NL views community consultation as essential to ensure the diversity and inclusion of stakeholder groups and their voices at various stages in the development of work programmes. Therefore, Open Science NL seeks to collaborate not only work with representatives of established institutions and covenant partners but also to work closely with the broader community of experts. Hence, Open Science NL proposes to structure community engagement along two complementary lines of action: consultative, through broad community consultation, and advisory, through expert advisory panels. Open Science NL is organised into four closely connected programme lines, each with its own programme leader. Community engagement activities will be organised around the four programme lines.

The consultative aspects of community engagement will be led by the programme leaders, who in addition to being experts in their thematic areas, are already well connected with their respective communities. Section 1 explains how Open Science NL will tap into these communities to receive valuable insights and broad, diverse and inclusive input directly from the communities.

The advisory element of community engagement will be centred around advisory panels. These are smaller groups of independent experts, which will offer each of the Open Science NL programme leaders expert guidance and strategic advice in developing effective work programmes and funding instruments that take into account community needs and advance the transition to open science. The members of these panels will be appointed through a transparent process. The panels will be guided by terms of reference, which will define the structure and the work of these panels. Section 2 outlines the approach to advisory panels in more detail.

1 Community consultation

Purpose

Through the process of community consultation, the Open Science NL team will receive valuable insights regarding the challenges and opportunities associated with the implementation of open science. A community here refers to the community of practitioners in a broad sense. It may refer to groups of researchers and professional support staff. It may also refer to infrastructures, to support services, national organisations, or domain- and discipline-specific organisations.

The landscape differs per programme line. Therefore, effective consultation strategies also differ. What is common for all programme lines is that, as experts in their fields, the programme leaders are already part of their respective communities. This means that they are in a position to build consultation strategies that, wherever possible, build around existing communities, their communication channels, meetings and events (including broader events, such as the Open Science Festival) to capitalise on and strengthen the existing community initiatives and to prevent consultation fatigue.

Sections 1.1 to 1.3 below sketch the existing community landscape and preferred consultation strategies per programme line, with the exception of open research software and FAIR data which are discussed jointly. Annex 1 contains a detailed community mapping per programme line. In addition to the consultation strategies laid out below, individuals are welcome to bring ideas and suggestions at any time directly to the programme leaders via the [Open Science NL website](#).

1.1 Open scholarly communication

Community landscape

In the open scholarly communication landscape, the community dedicated to open access is well-developed and highly connected. This community is strongly embedded within the universities and more specifically their libraries. People know how to reach out to one other, formally and informally. In recent years, there has been a growing need and interest from other stakeholders, besides the permanent core (i.e. UNL, UKB), to join this community: universities of applied sciences, KNAW- and NWO-institutes, STZ-hospitals ('Samenwerkende Topklinische Ziekenhuizen'), etc.

Consultation strategy

In general, the Dutch-based community currently active in open scholarly communication is well organised (see Annex 1). The broader range of stakeholders is more scattered and less aligned. Therefore, a two-track consultation strategy is proposed to be as inclusive as possible. One is aimed at the existing networks to facilitate current innovations, developments and implementations. The other is aimed at organisations and institutions that only recently started thinking about and implementing open scholarly communication policies, with the goal of supporting them in the process.

The community consultation can happen through multiple channels:

- In-person workshops or meetings (online or in-person; at least once a year) aimed at obtaining input from and stimulating conversations with the communities on the challenges and the most effective solutions to address them, as well as feedback on the (proposed) funding instruments. It is proposed that, as much as possible, these workshops will coincide with existing events (e.g. UKB-network meetings, open science festivals) or meeting structures and will be adapted to the level of knowledge and expertise of the participants.
- Online (international) consultations to ensure that the consultations are as wide and as inclusive as possible, in parallel to in-person workshops, and aligned with international developments in the area of open scholarly communication.

1.2 Open research hardware, software and FAIR data

Community landscape

There is some overlap between the open research hardware, software and FAIR data communities. With the exception of open research hardware, the communities are diverse and relatively mature. Therefore, the goal of the community consultation is to solicit input from the existing communities (for an overview, see Annex 1).

Consultation strategy

Given the overlap between the open research software, hardware and FAIR data communities, a joint community consultation strategy is proposed. This is in order to avoid consultation fatigue (caused by repeatedly approaching the same stakeholders for feedback) and also to promote synergies and cross-fertilisation of ideas. The community consultation will happen through multiple channels:

- In-person workshops aimed at obtaining input from the communities on the challenges and the most effective solutions to address them, as well as feedback on funding instruments. It is proposed that as much as possible, the workshops will coincide with existing events (e.g. LCRDM meetings, open science festivals).

1.3 Citizen science and societal engagement

Community landscape

In the Netherlands there are multiple communities representing specific parts of societal engagement and citizen science. Societal engagement predominantly consists of the science communication communities, which largely exist separately from the citizen science communities. Few people are part of both communities and there's little interaction between the two, such as cross-over in attending events, symposia and / or trainings. Communities within these two fields of interest generally represent diverse perspectives (such as science journalism, press offices, participation and dialogue, citizen science) and vary in their levels of organisational development. For example, some organisations are formally established as an association ('vereniging') with appointed community managers, while others are loosely organised on the basis of voluntary activity without any formal structure. Annex 1 provides an overview of the stakeholders within the current community landscape.

The goal of community consultation for the programme line citizen science and societal engagement is to receive feedback and input about challenges and opportunities related to the citizen science and societal engagement topics.

Consultation strategy

The primary consultation strategy will be via the Citizen Science NL network. However, given the diverse nature of societal engagement and science communication and citizen science communities in terms of organisational development, their lack of interconnectedness and the dispersed nature of citizen scientists in the Netherlands, different media and platforms will be used. Target platforms will be adjusted according to the needs and development of these dynamic communities.

Consultation methods may include:

- Workshops or meetings (online or in-person; at least once a year) aimed at obtaining input from the communities on the challenges and the most effective solutions to address them, as well as feedback on funding instruments.
- Different communication channels such as messenger apps, social media and/or newsletter(s).

2 Advisory panels

Purpose and role

Open Science NL has advisory panels with a minimum of 5 and a maximum of 14 members. The advisory panels are established to provide expert guidance and strategic advice to the programme leaders in developing effective work programmes and funding instruments that take into account community needs and that advance the transition to open science.

Organisation

Each advisory panel is chaired by the corresponding Open Science NL programme leader and supported by a secretary. In addition, another member of the Open Science NL team will join as the co-chair. If necessary, other Open Science NL office members can also attend the meetings. The panels are conceived as fora for bringing together broad representation and professional expertise in the areas of each of the main programme lines.

The following principles and guidelines apply:

- Members are experts on content (e.g. data infrastructures) and/or context (e.g. what mechanisms work in different institutional contexts) related to the panel they join. Profiles for panel members of each of the four programme lines can be found in Annex 2.
- Members are appointed for 2-4 years, with the exception of the launch panel, when 40-60% of the panel members are appointed for 2 years and 40-60% for 3 years to ensure continuity of the panel's work. Panel members can re-apply and be re-appointed for a maximum of one additional term.
- There is one additional open seat for guest members, who may contribute to a particular meeting with their specific expertise, and their participation may therefore vary from meeting to meeting.
- Members do not represent the organisation they are affiliated with while performing the work of the panel.
- While panel membership is not restricted to experts from organisations based in the Netherlands, the majority of the panel members must be affiliated with Dutch organisations to ensure sufficient understanding of the Dutch landscape.
- Members act in compliance with the [NWO Code Strategy and Policy Advice](#).
- Membership composition will be guided by NWO's diversity and inclusion policy.
- Terms of reference (see Annex 3) define the purpose, membership, roles and responsibilities, and the way the advisory panels will work.

List of annexes

- Annex 1: Community mapping per programme line
- Annex 2: Member profiles of advisory panels per programme line
- Annex 3: Terms of reference for the Open Science NL advisory panels

Annex 1 Community mapping per programme line

The document below maps relevant communities per programme line within Open Science NL, with the exception of open research software and FAIR data which are presented jointly.

1.1 Citizen science and societal engagement communities

List of 'formal' communities (the list is not exclusive)

Community/network	Description	Website/contact
Citizen Science NL (CS-NL)	Established in 2022. Received funding in 2024 from Open Science NL. Broad reach to citizen science practitioners (researchers and citizens), regular newsletters and meetings	https://www.cs-nl.network/
National expertise centre science & society (NEWS)	Established in 2024 and forms a centre for science communication expertise (including public engagement).	https://wetenschapensamenleving.nl/
SciCom NL	Dutch association for science communication; 200+ members including (science communication) researchers, freelancers, students, communication advisors, press officers etc.	https://www.scicom.nl/

List of local citizen science expertise or public engagement clusters (the list is not exclusive)

Community/network	Description	Website/contact
5 Citizen Science hubs	5 Citizen Science hubs funded by Open Science NL in 2025.	https://citizenscience.nl/hubs/
Kennisknooppunt participatie	Expertise center for participation within governmental organisations at Ministry of Water and Infrastructure	https://kennisknooppuntparticipatie.nl/
Citizen Science RIVM	Local expertise centre citizen science; coordinator of the samen meten platform	https://www.rivm.nl/burgerwetenschap
Waag futurelab	Research labs: smart citizen lab (Amsterdam):	https://waag.org/nl/lab/smart-citizens-lab/

Important stakeholders without any organised representation are:

- Researchers and research staff studying citizen science, public engagement, science communication, researchers with focus on action research and/or transdisciplinary research at universities, UMCs, universities of applied sciences or other organisations in the kingdom of the Netherlands
- Living labs and Fieldlabs² (where citizens, artists, technologists, businesses and public sector organisations come together)
- Dutch stakeholders who are part of European citizen science projects
- Communication departments of universities and UMCs involved in or with focus on participatory science communication

1.2 Open scholarly communication communities

The table below outlines the communities and networks operating predominantly in the Netherlands and which are important and relevant to the open scholarly communication programme line.

Community/network	Description	Website/contact
UKB (Dutch University Libraries) working group Open Access	The working group focuses on finding common goals and alignment of actions of university libraries on open access. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Mailing list and 6 meetings a year. End of year in-person strategy meeting. – Managed by chair and secretary of the Working Group. 	https://ukb.nl/werkgroepen/open-access/

² Further reading: [The ministry of economic affairs \(RVO\)'s study on living labs](#) and [the Rathenau Institute's report on living labs in the Netherlands](#).

Community/network	Description	Website/contact
UKB/SURF licence group	Licence managers Working Group. Responsible for the national read & publish (deals). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Mailing list and hybrid meetings. – Annual meeting with larger stakeholder groups (universities of applied sciences)). – Managed by SURF. 	https://ukb.nl/werkgroepen/licenties/
New University Presses/Library based publishing services	Network of local open access university presses. Received Open Science NL funding in 2025 for strengthening the network. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Regular meetings. The network will become a new Working Group in UKB. – Managed by Natalia Grygierczyk. 	https://nups.nl/
Openjournals.nl (user groups)	Journal editors community facilitated by openjournals.nl. Particularly relevant for advocacy on diamond open access.	www.openjournals.nl
OSC-NL	Open Science Communities in the Netherlands is a network of coordinators of Dutch Open Science Communities (OSC). Received Open Science NL funding in 2024 for strengthening the network. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Local mailing lists 	https://www.osc-nl.com/
National graduate and research schools	National graduate/research schools provide PhD candidates with the opportunity to come into contact with fellow PhD candidates from other universities. They offer training in both methodology and area specific knowledge for example on open access.	no website
Recognition and Rewards project groups/communities	The Dutch academic community is working towards a new balance in recognising and rewarding academics. All participants have set up committees and working groups that work on the Recognition and Rewards in their organisation. The participants can be found here . <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Annual conference – Mailing list – RRview community platform 	https://recognitionrewards.nl/
Netwerk Auteursrechten Informatiepunten (NAI)	This network focuses on author rights and copyright, but also on open access developments and open educational resource (OER).	https://auteursrechten.nl/
Samenwerkingsverband Hogeschoolbibliotheken (SHB), werkgroep Licenties	The members of the Licences Working Group represent all SHB members regarding the conclusion of content licences. They organise two LCP days per year, on which they share knowledge, for example by inviting publishers on topics such as e-books and open access.	https://www.shb-online.nl/shb-werk-projectgroepen/shb-werkgroep-licenties/

In addition, there are important international networks to be considered. The programme leader is actively involved in some of these networks, which helps to stay up to date with the international developments. The table below offers an overview of the most important international networks for open scholarly communication. Note that these are merely the most important networks, the list is not intended to be exhaustive.

Community/network	Description	Website/contact
LIBER (working group open access)	The Association of European Research Libraries is a professional association of national and university research libraries in Europe. A large community, one of their focus points is open access and open science (skills). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Annual conference – Winter event – Mailing list – Working groups/communities 	www.libereurope.org
OA2020 / OAfwd	OA2020 is a global alliance committed to accelerating the transition to open access.	https://oa2020.org/be-informed/#oa2020
OASPA	The Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association is a non-profit trade association of open access journal and book publishers. Areas of interest are equitable and transparent open scholarly communication. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Mailing list – Annual conference – Webinars 	https://oaspa.org/
cOALition S	Community of expert leads coordinated by cOALition S. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Mailing list – Website – Community engagements – The programme leader is part of the expert group. 	www.coalition-s.org/ https://www.coalition-s.org/experts/
Science Europe	Community of funding bodies in Europe. One of the interests and priorities is equitable open access (e.g. diamond open access)	www.scienceeurope.org
Open Research Europe	Open Research Europe (ORE) is an open access publishing platform established in 2021 by the European Commission to support researchers funded by the European Commission. 2026 will be the year of a significant evolution of the platform. This new phase expands ORE beyond its original European Commission funding model to become a collective effort supported by 16 national funders and research institutions across Europe, alongside continued European Commission involvement. The programme leader is member (chair) of the Executive Committee.	www.ore.eu

Community/network	Description	Website/contact
OPERAS	<p>OPERAS is the Research Infrastructure supporting open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) in the European Research Area.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Mailing list – Special Interest Groups 	https://operas-eu.org/
National Open Science programmes	<p>Several countries (e.g. France, Finland, Spain, Ireland) have national open science programmes, with a strong interest in open access and open scholarly communication.</p>	no website

1.3 Open research hardware, software and FAIR data communities

The table below outlines the communities and networks operating predominantly in the Netherlands and which are important and relevant to both the open research software and the FAIR data. As of July 2026, there are no formal national open research hardware networks in the Netherlands (to be addressed through funding instrument 2.3 of the Open Science NL Work Programme 2026-2027).

Community/network	Description	Website/contact
LCRDM	National Coordination Point Research Data Management <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Mailing list and network days twice a year – Managed by SURF 	https://lcrdm.nl/
DSiG	Data Stewards Interest Group <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Mailing list and hybrid meetings once every 1-2 months – Managed by Health-RI 	https://www.dtls.nl/about/community/interest-groups/data-stewards-interest-group/
4TU.ResearchData community	Community for those interested in research data and software (primarily from technical universities). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Newsletter, working groups and community meetings 2 times per year – Managed by 4TU.ResearchData 	https://community.data.4tu.nl/
TDCC communities	There are three Thematic Digital Competence Centres and each has its own community.	https://tdcc.nl/
LDCC network	Network of local digital competence centres <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Mailing list, regular meetings – Managed by SURF 	https://lcrdm.nl/dcc/
RDNL	Research Data Netherlands (collaboration between 4TU.ResearchData, DANS, SURF and Health-RI) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Particularly relevant to training 	https://researchdata.nl/en/
OSC-NL	Open Science Communities in the Netherlands is a network of coordinators of Dutch Open Science Communities (OSC).	https://www.osc-nl.com/
NL-RSE	People developing and contributing to research software. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Mailing list and occasional meet-ups – Managed by the Netherlands eScience Center 	https://nl-rse.org/

Community/network	Description	Website/contact
Research Software Training NL	Community of training coordinators from Dutch research initiatives delivering training in research software, programming skills, open-source code and applied data science. – Managed by the Netherlands eScience Center	https://researchsoftwaretraining.nl/
Netherlands Research Integrity Network	Collaboration, exchange and mutual learning in the field of research integrity. – Meetings, website and newsletters.	https://www.nrin.nl/
The NL Reproducibility Network (NLRN)	Consortium with the goal to increase the quality and efficiency of research in the Netherlands by coordinating, supporting and strengthening initiatives on reproducibility and transparency.	https://reproducibilitynetwork.nl/
National research schools	National research schools provide PhD candidates with the opportunity to come into contact with fellow PhD candidates from other universities. They offer training in both methodology and area specific knowledge.	Some examples can be found here: https://www.universiteitleiden.nl/en/science/graduate-school-of-science/current-phd-candidates/research-schools
ReproducibiliTea(s)	An initiative helping create local Open Science journal clubs to discuss diverse issues around reproducibility and open science.	https://reproducibilitea.org/

In addition, for both open research software and FAIR data there are important international networks to be considered. The programme leaders are part of these networks, which helps them stay abreast of their fields internationally. The table below offers an overview of the most important international networks for open research software and FAIR data. Note that these are merely the most important networks, the list is not intended to be exhaustive.

Community/network	Description	Website/contact
RDA	Research Data Alliance – Working and Interest Groups; plenary meeting twice a year.	https://www.rd-alliance.org/
ReSa	Research Software Alliance – Task Forces, Community Consultations; Funders Forum meets once a month.	https://www.researchsoft.org/
CODATA	Panel on Data of the International Science Council	https://codata.org/
EOSC Association	The EOSC Association governs the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) initiative. – Newsletter and meetings for members two times per year.	https://eosc.eu/
Software Sustainability Institute	UK-based institution facilitating the advancement of software in research.	https://www.software.ac.uk/

Annex 2 Member profiles of advisory panels per programme line

2.1 Open scholarly communication advisory panel

The advisory panel on open scholarly communication will consist of individuals with expertise and experience in, but not limited to, the following areas relevant to open scholarly communication:

- Open access
- Open publishing workflows
- Open publishing infrastructures
- Open source publishing software
- Preprints
- Open peer review
- Reproducible publishing
- Open access books
- Open textbooks
- Open research information (systems)
- Training and skills for open access and scholarly communication
- Open access in the context of societal engagement / citizen science
- Open scholarly communication in the context of discussions around equity, diversity and inclusion
- The panel will have representation from diverse disciplines and diverse roles, including researchers, research support staff, policy experts and advocacy experts in academia

All members of the panel are able to provide substantive input and give direction to the open scholarly communication programme line of Open Science NL. Members will:

- Provide independent advice and contribute expertise and insights. In doing so, they act independently of the institution they are affiliated with.
- Have insight into the open scholarly communication landscape nationally and internationally.
- Have complementary expertise, so that the panel as a whole covers a broad range of knowledge, experience and expertise.
- Keep abreast of developments in the area of open scholarly communication, its relation to other areas of open science and recognition and rewards and their respective disciplines or areas of expertise.

2.2 Citizen science and societal engagement advisory panel

Members of the citizen science and societal engagement advisory panel should have one or more of the following expertise:

- Citizen science
- Public/societal engagement
- (Participatory) science communication
- Research on dialogue/active listening
- Community building
- Ethics
- Science journalism / science musea
- Science & technology studies
- Transdisciplinary research
- Action research
- Recognition & rewards of science communication, public engagement and/or citizen science

Alternatively, members are a representative of the following:

- Governmental or semi-governmental organisations involved in citizen science projects
- Patient organisations/ advocacy groups or advocates with a broad network
- Grass-root community projects involved in citizen science
- Libraries involved in citizen science
- Initiatives bringing science and society closer together

Members should see themselves in the following mission:

- Clear vision on and experience in involving people outside of academia in science and vice versa.
- Willingness to innovate and increase the inclusion of stakeholders outside of academia into academia.

2.3 Research software, hardware and data advisory panel

The advisory panel will consist of individuals with expertise and experience across the entire lifecycle pertaining, including:

- Training and skills for open research software, hardware and FAIR data
- Infrastructures and tools for open research software, hardware and FAIR data
- Software sustainability
- Open source software
- Open research hardware
- FAIR software and FAIR Data
- Computational reproducibility
- Software publication and citation
- Software management and software management plans
- Licences for software, hardware and data
- Community building
- Metadata and ontologies
- Confidential data (including privacy-sensitive data, as well as other types of data)
- Open research software and FAIR data in the context of a university
- Open research software and FAIR data in the context of a university medical centre
- Open research software and FAIR data in the context of a university of applied sciences
- Open research software and FAIR data in the context of a knowledge / research institute

The panel will have representation from diverse disciplines and diverse roles, including researchers, research software engineers, research support staff and policy experts.

All members of the panel are able to provide substantive input and give direction to Open Science NL.

Members will:

- Provide independent advice and contribute expertise and insights. In doing so, they act independently of the institution they are affiliated with.
- Have complementary expertise, so that the panel as a whole covers a broad range of knowledge, experience and expertise.

Annex 3 Terms of reference for the Open Science NL advisory panels

1 Purpose

The purpose of the advisory panels is to provide expertise, advice and recommendations to each of the programme leaders of Open Science NL. The panels aim to support the programme leaders in developing effective work programmes and funding instruments that take into account community needs and that advance the transition to open science.

2 Objectives

The panels will:

- offer their expertise, insights, and best practices to the programme leaders in support of the development and implementation of an effective work programme that addresses community needs;
- provide feedback on the design, feasibility and progress of funding instruments; and
- assist in identifying challenges, opportunities, and emerging trends within the field of open science.

3 Membership

3.1 Members

Each advisory panel consists of a minimum of 5 and a maximum of 14 members, including experts on both content (e.g. data infrastructures or open software) and / or context (e.g. universities or universities applied sciences). The panels will be diverse and encompass expertise from various disciplines and sectors related to open science. Panel members have a strong commitment to open science principles and practices. Membership composition will be guided by NWO's diversity and inclusion policy.

3.2 Guiding principles

Members of the advisory panels uphold the values of [the Science Europe Values Framework](#):

- Autonomy/freedom, care & collegiality,
- Collaboration,
- Equality, diversity & inclusion, integrity and ethics,
- Openness and transparency.

3.3 Recruitment of members

Panel members are identified through a public call for applications to stimulate transparency and diversity. In addition, individuals can nominate candidates (with their permission) for the panels. Both applicants and nominees must complete a concise form consisting of 3 to 4 open-ended questions. These questions aim to gather relevant information about their qualifications, commitment to the panel's objectives, relevant expertise, motivation to join, and ability to manage potential conflicts of interest. This process ensures a comprehensive evaluation of each individual's suitability for the panel. Applications are open to international experts based outside the Netherlands; however, the majority of the panel members must be affiliated with Dutch organisations to ensure sufficient understanding of the Dutch landscape among panel members.

3.4 Selection of members

The Open Science NL team is responsible for selecting the panel members from the received applications, in consultation with existing members of the respective advisory panel.

3.5 Duration

The appointment term for panel members is three years, with the possibility of reappointment for a maximum of one additional term. However, to ensure the continuity of each panel's work in the long term, panels will be initiated with approximately 40-60% of the members appointed for a two-year term, and the remaining 40-60% appointed for the full three-year term.

3.6 Guest members

Every panel reserves one seat for guest members, providing an opportunity for individuals with specific expertise to contribute to a particular meeting. Therefore, participation of these guest members may vary from one meeting to another.

3.7 Conflict of interest

Members and guest members do not represent the organisation they are affiliated with while performing the work of the panel. Furthermore, members act in compliance with the [NWO Code Strategy and Policy Advice](#).

4 Roles and responsibilities

4.1 Chair and co-chair

The chair of each advisory panel is the corresponding Open Science NL programme leader, who is assisted by a secretary. The co-chair is a programme leader from a different Open Science NL programme line to foster collaboration and cross-fertilisation of ideas and to promote a comprehensive and coherent approach among the panels. The chair and co-chair have the following responsibilities:

- facilitating panel meetings and ensuring productive discussions;
- setting the agenda for the meetings in consultation with the panel members;
- making sure that each meeting is planned effectively and that matters are dealt with in an orderly and efficient manner;
- encouraging participation of all members in the discussions; and
- summarising the conclusions of discussions and any agreed follow-up actions.

4.2 Members

Panel members (and guest members) have the following responsibilities:

- participating actively in panel meetings and discussions. Members who regularly miss panel meetings may be removed from the panel.
- reviewing and providing feedback on work programmes, funding instruments, and other relevant documents; and
- providing expertise, insights, and recommendations related to the programme line.

The panels might occasionally commission position papers into specific issues/topics, as appropriate and relevant.

5 Meetings

5.1 Frequency and format

Meetings will be held at least twice per year. 50% of panel members, rounded up if uneven, attending a meeting constitute a quorum. Remote participation will be facilitated.

5.2 Documents for the meetings

The chair will develop the meeting agendas, taking into account any input from panel members. Agendas and any supporting materials will be circulated prior to each meeting, allowing sufficient time for preparation. Any other documents to be considered by the panel will be decided by the chair in consultation with the panel members.

5.3 Publication of agenda and meeting minutes

If possible, anonymised agendas and meeting minutes will be published on www.openscience.nl and the [Zenodo](#) repository to facilitate the findability and long-term availability of the documents for interested parties.

6 Resources

6.1 Secretarial support

The panels will be provided with secretarial support for:

- scheduling meetings;
- coordinating meeting logistics, including room bookings, AV equipment setup, and links for remote participants;
- distributing meeting agendas and relevant reading materials; and
- taking and distributing meeting minutes.

6.2 Communication support

The panels will be provided with communications support for:

- publishing documents related to Open Science NL on the organisation's website and Zenodo platform.
- a shared digital space for sharing and collaborating on documents with panel members.

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Contact address:

Laan van Nieuw Oost-Indië 300

2593 CE Den Haag

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